

**Dynamic Eclipse Broadcast (DEB) Initiative
Solar Eclipse Observing Procedure & Training**

1 April 2024

(DEB Information at debinitiative.org)

Filter is removed only during actual eclipse: NOT during training

Setup: Tripod & Cables, Camera Rotation, Resolution, Focus

Partial Phase Procedure

Totality Procedure

Calibration Data: Flats and Darks

Polar Axis Alignment

Times

Expected Meridian Flip: _____

Start setup \geq 1 hour before 1st Contact: _____

Start solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py 2 minutes before 1st Contact: _____

1st Contact: _____

Stop photosphere 10 minutes before 2nd Contact: _____

Check focus and alignment

Start totality.py 1 minute before 2nd Contact: _____

2nd Contact: _____

3rd Contact: _____

Cover telescope immediately and stop totality.py

4th Contact: _____

Stop photosphere 2 minutes after 4th Contact: _____

___ Collect Calibration data after 4th Contact

___ **Backup data!!!**

How do I know what times to put in the top of the Procedure?

The times for your location can be found online. We really like the site by Xavier Jubier, http://xjubier.free.fr/en/site_pages/SolarEclipsesGoogleMaps.html.

You can select different eclipses then find your location (clicking on the location, or using search bar in upper left corner). You are then provided with the information panel shown below. These are the times you use to fill in the **Bold** highlighted times. You must calculate the others based on the information given.

What do 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th contact mean?

- 1st contact (C1) = start of eclipse at your location
- 2nd contact (C2) = start of totality, if any, at your location
- 3rd contact (C3) = end of totality at your location
- 4th contact (C4) = end of eclipse at your location

How do I pick a good site?

- Clear viewing of the Sun for full duration of eclipse (no trees, buildings etc. obscuring view)
- Safe viewing area (think falling off of a roof, extremely rough terrain, or getting hit by a motorist type of thing here)
- Power and internet access? (depends on if you plan on bringing batteries and other forms of connectivity, but good to consider)
- Can you get to the site on the day of the eclipse? (some locations might be closed on the day of)

1. Set up tripod and telescope
 - a. Setup tripod and attach pier extension with equatorial base attached
 - i. If using external leveling device, level pier extension before attaching equatorial base
 - ii. If using bubble level, level equatorial base
 - b. Attach mount to equatorial base
 - c. Ensure azimuth correction screws on mount are centered by following these instructions:

- i. Loosen azimuth locking screws
- ii. Screws on both sides should be equally exposed (see green arrows in image above) when snugged up
 1. Snug up by turning screws in opposite directions
 2. If not centered when snug, turn screws in same direction to rotate mount until they are centered
- iii. Snug up azimuth locking screws
- d. Use a compass to point mount North (geographic) by loosening pier extension and rotating entire assembly
 - i. Red clutches should be on North side of mount
 - ii. Be aware of your magnetic declination to assist in rough alignment
 1. <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml?>
 2. Whatever method you use to account for magnetic declination just remember:
 - a. 5° East declination means true north is 5° WEST of your compass needle
 - b. 5° West declination means true north is 5° EAST of your compass needle

What is this magnetic declination stuff about?

Compasses point to magnetic North, which is usually not the same at 'true,' geographic North.

Magnetic declination is the variation from true and compass north.

We have to account for this variation when setting up our telescope.

One way is to use a phone app, such as, 'Compass and Altimeter' by PixelProse SARL

Another is to correct using your compass. The image below from,

<https://www.princeton.edu/~oa/manual/mapcompass2.shtml>, provides a visual of magnetic declination across the US,

and the next image helps visualize how to adjust where the telescope is pointing (as mentioned in the procedure, you can find your declination at, <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml>)

Magnetic Declination
Example of 20° East and West

Black arrow points to True North, while Orange arrow is magnetic North

← 20° East

20° West →

Point equatorial base towards the black arrow direction to correct for declination

- iii. Tighten pier extension back down – Actually “Tighten” this part. . .the only one on the setup to “tighten”
- e. Check/adjust the latitude setting on the equatorial base following these steps:
 - i. Find your latitude with Google Maps or <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml?>
 - ii. Loosen latitude locking lever
 - iii. Use latitude adjustment screw to adjust until latitude indicator is close to your latitude.
 - iv. Snug up latitude locking lever
- f. Level mount with bubble level if you haven’t already done so in part 1a
- g. Attach counter weight bar
 - i. Be careful not to cross thread when screwing in
- h. Attach counter weight
 - i. Ensure larger hole in counter weight is facing bottom of counter weight bar
 - ii. Be careful until safety nut is in place on end of counter weight bar
 - iii. Ensure nut on counter weight facing out (to avoid hitting mount later)
- i. Attach telescope to mount – objective lens pointing north
- j. Attach solar finder if using one
 - i. Provided finder should be mounted with hole towards *front* of scope (see image to Right)
- k. Balance mount along both axes (Dec/RA) following these steps:
 - i. Balance weight of scope with counter weight along RA axis (Bigger clutch)
 - ii. Snug RA clutch down with telescope and counter weight horizontal to ground
 - iii. Loosen Dec clutch (smaller one) and balance front of scope with back of scope
 - iv. Snug Dec clutch up and loosen RA clutch
 - v. Return to Counter weight down position
 - vi. Snug clutches (**Do Not Over Tighten, But mount should feel stable**)
- l. Use arrow buttons on back of mount to square up body of mount with equatorial base (see image below)
- m. Loosen DEC clutch (smaller one) to allow for lining scope up with mount and base
- n. Check all clutches snug

Using buttons to adjust mount position

Example of proper Counter weight down position

2. Plug the camera and mount into USB3.0 ports on the laptop, make sure the cables are secure and have room to move without tension, and turn mount on.
 - a. We will be orienting the camera with the cable pointing 'up' as seen in the images below. This will be fine-tuned later in the procedure, but start in this general configuration

3. **Ensure telescope is NOT pointed at the Sun**
 - a. Remove telescope cap
 - b. Attach solar filter
4. Open SharpCap on computer
 - a. Go to "Scripting" > "Run Script ..."
 - i. Select "startup.py" and run
 - b. *If you do not see a window for iOptron pop up after SharpCap opens follow these steps:*
 - i. *On the right of the SharpCap screen, scroll down to "Scope Controls" at bottom of the "Camera Control Panel" and click "Connected"*
 - ii. *If that doesn't work*
 1. *Go to the "File" dropdown in the upper left of SharpCap*
 - a. *Select "SharpCap Settings" > "Hardware"*
 - b. *In "Mount > "Select Hardware" select "iOptron . . . SkyHunter Mount"*
 - c. *Optionally, you can select "Connect Hardware automatically when opening a camera" in the "General" section of the "Hardware" page.*
 - c. In "Device Information" section of new iOptron window select "Mount Panel"
5. Setup mount with iOptron Commander
 - a. Ensure "Mount Model SkyHunter EQ Mode" in upper left corner of Mount Panel
 - i. **If not:**
 1. *Close iOptron*
 2. *Turn off power to mount*
 3. *Push and hold center button on back of mount`*

4. Turn power on
 5. Release button when lights on mount stop flashing
 6. Should now see one light illuminated on back of mount, that is not the S
 - b. Ensure mount set to Northern Hemisphere in middle right of Mount Panel
 - i. **If not:**
 1. Hold the center button down until S light begins to flash
 2. Release center button and then tap it until S light goes out
 - c. On mobile device, turn on wifi and select mount
 - i. SH_XXXXXX
 - ii. Accept any warning about connectivity (doesn't actually provide you with wifi)
 - d. Open iOptronCommanderMobile on mobile device
 - e. Click "Tap to connect to iOptron mounts"
 - f. Click "Time and Site"
 - g. Click "Sync Current Device Time to Mount" and "Sync Current Device Location to Mount"
 - h. **Take screenshot/picture of phone screen, or write down Lat/Long**
 - i. You should **close app on phone** at this time if you don't intend to use app and shutoff wifi connection to mount (can crash frequently)
6. **Ensure the Solar Filter is on the telescope** and the scope is in counter weight down position with clutches snug.
 7. Use iOptron Commander to slew (goto) the Sun following these instructions:
 - a. Select "Zero Position"
 - i. "Set Current Position as Zero Position"
 1. *If using same location multiple times with same mount setup, can use "Goto Zero Position"*
 - b. Select "Slew"
 - i. Select "Star Catalog" in upper left panel
 - ii. In "Catalog Name" on right, select "Solar System"
 - iii. Use "Catalog Number" +/- buttons until "Object Name" = 'Sun' (#9)
 - iv. Select "Confirm Slew" in bottom left of window
 - v. Click OK on warning about viewing Sun **after verifying solar filter on scope**
 1. Be very conscious of counterweight, levers and cables hitting/catching on mount during slewing
 2. You can click "Stop" in iOptron main window to stop slew if a problem occurs, and select confirm slew again after problem resolved
 8. Once slew completed use your preferred method below to locate sun if not in viewing window:
 - a. ENSURE 'ZOOM' IN UPPER RIGHT OF SHARPCAP IS MINIMIZED!
 - b. YOU WILL PROBABLY NEED TO INCREASE IOPTRON RATE OF MOVEMENT TO SEE LARGE SCALE MOVEMENT (16X IS TOO SLOW) (see image below)

- c. Solar finder
 - i. Move iOptron arrows at bottom right of SharpCap while looking for white dot on back of solar finder. **Do Not Look Directly at the Sun!!!**
 - d. Exposure trick
 - i. You can turn the exposure up on SharpCap camera controls on the right of SharpCap (~300ms or larger) to overexpose the sun, and make it visible before the Sun is actually in the field of view.
 1. Once you see a region illuminated, move controls to move illuminated region into center of view
 2. You will have to decrease exposure as you get closer to finding the Sun
 - e. Shadow minimization
 - i. Watch shadow of scope on the ground and move with arrows until shadow size is minimized
 - f. SharpCap spiral search function in scope controls
 - i. Press and hold spiral button on iOptron controls at bottom right of SharpCap
9. Once Sun is in center of screen, hit "Sync" on iOptron Mount Control Panel and accept warnings about viewing the Sun. **DO NOT FORGET TO ACCEPT WARNING!!! – NOT ACCEPTING WARNING CAN CAUSE SHARPCAP TO FAIL. YOU MAY HAVE TO MINIMIZE SHARPCAP TO SEE WARNING WINDOW.**
 10. Adjust exposure (~1 – 3 ms) – Sun should appear grayish instead of bright white. To get the proper exposure follow these steps:

- a. Use the SharpCap histogram
 - i. Go to the Tools tab at the top of SharpCap and select Histogram
 - ii. The target is 72% - 80% exposure on either the "Histogram" or the "Histogram Stretch" as seen below

11. Focus procedure:

- a. Rough focus with full view of sun in view screen
 - i. Focus region will be $\sim 3/4$ of a turn from fully counterclockwise (from back of scope) for DEB scopes with provided adapter and extension tubes
 - ii. You will probably have to adjust exposure as focus changes: use the histogram for this as described in step 10
- b. Once rough focus complete, zoom into an area of interest (sunspot, solar limb)
 - i. Make small adjustments to obtain best focus
 1. Think eye doctor: better . . . worse . . . better . . . worse . . .
- c. Repeat step b) until best focus is achieved. Stop zooming in when image is pixelated.
- d. Zoom back out until sun fully visible in SharpCap screen

12. Select the round reticule in SharpCap by hitting in the upper right of the tool bar, twice.

- a. You will get a settings window if you push this button too many times, but not a problem. . . just hit the button again

13. With Sun in the SharpCap viewing window, adjust the camera orientation using the camera orientation ring on the telescope until left/right arrows correspond to horizontal motion and up arrow corresponds to vertical motion

- a. Use the reticule lines or side of viewing window as an aide to getting this as close as possible. It will help with drift alignment and data processing.
- b. Depending on which side of the mount your scope is on (West/East) the horizontal/R.A. buttons may not match left/right.
- c. Recenter Sun and "Sync" on iOptron Mount control panel again. **Remember to accept any warnings about viewing the Sun in iOptron.**

14. Drift Alignment procedure from now until 2 minutes before 1st contact – See Alignment Procedures at end of this document.

- a. New camera alignment might cause reaction of adjustments to be reversed, but still use the same procedure
- b. If using nighttime polar alignment or block alignment, still check for acceptable drift now, and make any adjustments with drift alignment procedure

15. Run Solar Photosphere data collection from 2 minutes before 1st contact until 10 minutes before 2nd contact (totality) and after 3rd contact (end of totality)

- a. “Scripting” > “Run Script ...” > “solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py”
 - i. Start upload.exe with the windows shortcut
 - ii. “solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py” **should only be terminated by hitting the ‘STOP’ button in the upper right of SharpCap.**

1. The shutdown procedure can take some time, depending on what level of processing and uploading is occurring in the background
2. Any other shutdown method can lead to errors creeping in. If there is a problem you can always shutdown and restart SharpCap, and then rerun ‘startup.py’

16. Occasionally monitor quality of processed images in C:\DEB\Upload to ensure focus and exposure are still good (**changing temperatures will affect the focus!**).

- a. If you need to change focus, repeat fine focus steps in 11b – c
 - i. If having trouble, you can:
 - ii. stop solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py with the STOP button
 - iii. Repeat fine focus steps in 11b – c
 - iv. Restart “solar_photosphere.PSS_Upload.py”
 - v. Restart “upload.exe” with the shortcut if necessary (old code)

17. **Totality (ONLY IF IN PATH OF TOTALITY)**

10 minutes before 2nd contact, stop solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py with STOP button

Recheck and make corrections to focus following focusing procedure

- a. **Totality**
 - i. Before totality have someone stand in front of telescope or block it with an object (paper etc.) and carefully remove the solar filter
 - ii. **1 minute before totality** run “Scripting” > “Run Script ...” > “totality.py”
 - iii. At totality have the person blocking the scope CAREFULLY step out of the way
 - iv. If you bumped the telescope removing the solar filter or stepping away: Carefully adjust the mount with iOptron to recenter the Sun.
- b. **ENJOY THE ECLIPSE**, occasionally check that the sun is in frame and the data is being collected, and adjust if possible. NOT MUCH YOU CAN DO HERE IF SOMETHING GOES WRONG. . . TRUST ME ☺
- c. After diamond ring at end of totality
 - i. DO NOT USE 2017 METHOD OF FORCIBLY TURNING SCOPE OFF OF THE SUN. . .

- YOU MAY NEVER GET YOUR CLUTCHES LOOSE AGAIN IF YOU DO. . .
- ii. Place something over objective lens (solar filter, piece of paper, etc.)
 - iii. Stop "Totality.py" with STOP button
 - iv. Check focus and centering of the sun after totality.py has shutdown
 1. Must click on the OK button to acknowledge totality.py has shut down if using new script
- d. **RESTART** 'solar_photosphere_PSS_Upload.py'

The following calibration procedures need to be completed after 4th contact

18. Release the clutches on the mount and turn the scope away from the sun to a region of the sky that is bright and clear (no clouds if possible).
 - a. **REMOVE CAP or SOLAR FILTER!**
 - b. Cover objective lens with patch of white cloth (light T-shirt) and use rubber band to secure

- c. Ensure covering not wrinkled, but not so tight stretches out material

- d. Open histogram in the SharpCap "Tools" dropdown menu
- e. Adjust exposure until histogram looks like image below: Right side of curve ~ 70%

- f. "Scripting" > "Run Script ..." > "flats.py"
 - i. This program will self terminate after ~ 1 minute

- 19. With the cover on the telescope (not the solar filter!) run: "Scripting" > "Run Script ..." > "darks.py"
 - a. This program will self terminate after ~ 5 - 6 minutes

Alignment Procedures

Drift Method

Follow these directions after the proper camera alignment has been achieved by step 12 above

*****) Remember, if you make an adjustment and the drift gets worse, just make the same adjustment in the opposite direction. If it switches to a different direction: congratulations! You are close, you just overshot your mark.**

- 1) Zoom in on a sunspot, or the limb (edge) of the sun if none available, using the SharpCap Zoom dropdown menu in the upper right of the toolbar until the image is pixelated.
- 2) Move the mouse cursor to the edge of the sunspot or limb
- 3) Watch to see how the image drifts with respect to the cursor
 - a. Note: the image will 'wobble' around, but this is normal
 - b. Looking for accumulated drift in one direction over time
- 4) Ideally aligned, the sunspot should drift no more than 2 pixels per minute horizontally, with no vertical drift
 - a. This will be difficult to achieve in a short amount of time
- 5) An acceptable drift is if the sunspot shows only eastward drift at ≤ 15 pixels per minute
- 6) If there is unacceptable drift, make adjustments with the azimuth adjustment screws or latitude adjustment screw based on the table below.
 - a. If you make a correction based on the table and the drift gets worse in the direction you were expecting improvement just reverse the direction of the correction.
 - b. **Don't forget to release and resecure the locking screws before/after adjustments respectively.**
- 7) After adjusting use mount controls to move sun back into the view screen and repeat until an acceptable amount of drift is obtained

<i>Image Drift</i>		<i>Correction</i>
<i>Scope on West side of mount Before Midday</i>	<i>Scope on East side of mount After Midday</i>	<i>See note below table for instructions</i>
North (up)	North (up)	Rotate mount to the East
South (down)	South (down)	Rotate mount to the West
East (left)	East (Right)	Adjust Latitude Upwards
West (right)	West (left)	Adjust Latitude Downwards

Azimuth adjustment notes:

We want to screw IN the screw on the side we want to move to, while simultaneously screwing OUT the screw on the opposite side:

- 1) To rotate the mount east
 - a. Release azimuth locking screws
 - b. Simultaneously: clockwise with the East Screw, counterclockwise with the West Screw

- c. Secure locking screws
- 2) To rotate the mount west
 - a. Release azimuth locking screws
 - b. Simultaneously: counterclockwise with the East screw, clockwise with the west screw
 - c. Secure locking screws

SharpCap Polar Alignment Method (Requires repeatable setup at location with Polaris and multiple nearby stars visible at night)

With clear viewing of Polaris

Open: *SharpCap > Tools > Polar Align*

Follow directions in alignment tool

End of Document

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